

**INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEES REWARD PROGRAMME ON
JOB PERFORMANCE IN NZOIA SUGAR COMPANY LIMITED
BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA**

Injendi Wycliffe,

Joash Migosi

University of Nairobi,
Kenya

Abstract:

This study aimed at investigating on how the current reward programme influence employees job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. Specifically, it aimed at finding out which aspects of reward programme functions well and which aspects could be further developed and improved in order to increase employee job performance. The research specific objectives were; (i) to establish the influence of promotion on employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County; (ii) to establish how training influence employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County and (iii) to examine the influence of flexible work systems on employee work motivation at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. The target population was 252 employees of Nzoia Sugar Company Limited. The target population comes from different departments. The study sample size was 76 employees obtained through stratified random sampling method. The descriptive research design was used. The data was collected through questionnaires and interviews. The data was prepared and analyzed by descriptive statistics and inferential statistics through the aid SPSS. Data was presented in form of tables, pie charts, and bar charts. The study used correlation analysis to bring out the relationship between the variables under study. Promotion of employees showed the greatest influence on employees job performance as it indicated the highest mean of 35.5 and hence based on these findings the company should implement promotional rewards to realize increase increased productivity of the employees. Promotional rewards are ranked no. 1 among other promotional rewards. This study will be of significance to the management of Nzoia Sugar Company limited in Bungoma County

to revise reward program policies for the purpose of increasing employee job performance, the study will enable the researcher to make recommendations to Nzoia Sugar Company administrators in Bungoma County, policy makers especially Kenya Sugar Board and any public sector in formulating policies and strategies to be employed to improve employee job performance in institutions of sugar manufacturing industry. The study will also be a source of reference for researchers intending to carry out further research on the influence of reward programs on employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company limited in Bungoma County or any other institution.

Keywords: reward, job, programme, performance, company, employee, promotion

1. Introduction

Today's reality in the global world is that people influence important aspects of organizational performance in a multitude of ways. The mix of people and systems mostly determine an organization's capabilities. Therefore, if an organization is to treat its employees as most important asset, it has to be knowledgeable about what it is that motivates people to reach their full potential. (Lawler, 2003), the primary focus of rewards is how organizations define the reward programme and communicate this in a manner that employees clearly understand the link between reward and employee job performance (Flynn, 1998). Effective reward system enhances employee motivation, employee productivity, all of which contribute to improved organizational performance (Deeprise, 1994). Baron (1983), argues that there is a close relationship between rewards and employee work motivation. He notes that if successful performance does in fact lead to organizational rewards, such performance could be motivational factors to employees under such conditions, and they can see that their efforts result in rewards. Consequently, they may be motivated to exert higher levels of effort on the job.

The notion of rewarding employees for "a job well done" has existed since the 19th century. (Schiller, 1996). Today some analysts have proposed that intrinsic rewards such as increased feelings of well-being achievement are better motivations of employees. Different motivation rewards may affect an employee in different ways at different points in time because conditions, needs and personal objectives are not static but in constant state of flux (Lawler, 2003). Motivation concerns on the people's perception and feelings on how they are treated as compared with others (Armstrong 2001). The argument is that people work well or motivated in accordance to what they regard as fair. Employees consider whether management has treated them fairly, when they look at what they receive for the effort they made. Maicibi (2003) agrees with this

that employee expect rewards or outcomes to broadly proportional to their effort. In this regard, Boddy and Patron (1998), give the formula below to illustrate the comparison.

Input (A) = Input (B).

Reward (A) = Reward (B).

Employee (A) compares the ratio of his/her input to his/her reward to that of employee B. If he/she feels the ratio are similar, he / she bound to be satisfied with treatment received. If he/she feels inadequately treated, he /she is bound to be dissatisfied. This dissatisfaction is likely to breed tension and frustration in such employees and their consequent work motivation may be negatively affected this may perhaps lower rewards. (Boddy and Patron 1998).

Motivation is based on how much one wants something and how likely he / she could get it (Bodden 2008). This is because the motivational force of every individual is influenced by his /her expectancies, valances, all of which depend on a personal way of perception. According to Victor Vroom (1964), he argues that motivation plus effort leads to performance which then leads to outcomes. He further argues that individuals exhibits motivated behavior when three conditions are fulfilled and these include: - Valance, Instrumentality and expectancy. The expectancy theory explains that any given situation, the greater the number and variety of rewards that are available to the employees to greater is the probability that extra effort will be exerted in attaining the set goals in the hope of getting the desired rewards Bodden, (2008). Gerald Cole (2004) agrees with this and explains that Vroom focused especially on the factors that are involved in stimulating an individual to put an effort in doing something since this is the basis of motivation. The outcomes are consequences of behavior. Vroom defines the anticipated satisfaction of an individual hopes to get from the outcome or reward. According to Vroom the three factors expectancy, instrumentality and valence combine to create a driving force which motivates an individual to put in effort and achieve a level of performance to be rewarded in the end, Rewards can be very motivating, helping to build feelings of confidence and satisfaction (Kelle, 1999). The rewards also reduce absenteeism of employees, and increases employee retention Jimenez (1999). Zigon, (1998), argues that individual employees will be highly motivated when they find rewards more valuable to them. Allen and Helms' (2002) research confirmed the importance of regular expressions of appreciation by managers and leaders to encourage behavior of employees to reach strategic goals. `

Jacob (2005) citing Van der post et al (1997) reported that the organization reward system should be perceived by employees as reinforcing the notion that most employees are good performer and there should be a linkage between reward and

employees are most motivated when they feel strongly connected to and valued by organization.

There is a positive association among work outcomes, public employees' motivation and performance related pay designs (Paarsch and Shearer 2000) whereas Wright (2007) implied the positive relationship between the availability of extrinsic rewards and organization. According to Hafiza et al, (2011), there is a positive relationship between extrinsic rewards and employee job performance.

A survey also shows that the employees were satisfied with extrinsic factors, such as working environment, their co-workers and the professional work climate, benefits, job securities and flexible or normal work hours (Pawloski, Suzanne Datta, and Pratine Houston, 2005). Another study performed by Baer, Oldham and Cummings, (2003), showed that extrinsic rewards were positive for employees occupying simple jobs and negative for employees having jobs that were difficult and challenging. Intrinsic benefits that arise from the job content it and have consequences for the psychological development of the employee (Williamson, Barnett & Bartol, 2009). It would appear that the greatest amount of motivation is present when people perform tasks that are both intrinsically and extrinsically rewarding (Lawler, 2003). A survey of it professionals working in state agencies and University of Louisiana USA, conducted in 2002, showed that employees were mostly satisfied with intrinsic factors such as the technical aspects of the work and working with new technologies.

The intellectual challenge and creativity require solving complex technical problems, the constant learning and master skills related to new technologies and a sense of contribution and pride in their accomplishment (Pawlowski, 2005) Human beings are motivated by requirements that fulfill their needs. These depend on many factors and vary by the individual requirements and necessary situation. Besides basic needs that range from food, clothing, medical and shelter, there is workplace that needs to be extended for acceptance and self-esteem (Khan et al, 2010).

Nzoia Sugar Company limited is located between Webuye and Bungoma town, Bungoma County. It was commissioned in 1978. The initial objectives for the insertion of Nzoia Sugar Company limited in Bungoma County were to increase country's GDP through exports, curb rural-urban migration, create employment and create self-sufficiency in sugar production. The company's shareholding structure-Kenya government (97.93%), fives ceil Babcock (1.13%) and industrial development bank (0.93%) The company was formed under companies Act cap 486 laws of Kenya with memorandum of articles of association.

Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County established reward systems since it was started in 1978, (Nzoia profile report 2009). The aim of the rewards was to

boost employee motivation. In spite of Nzoia Sugar Company Limited management efforts to reward employees for better services or increases their work motivation, the employees seem not to exhibit signs of well-motivated employees (Nzoia survey report, 2012). This has resulted into dissatisfied employees, late coming of employees, lack of commitment to the job, dodging some responsibilities which consequently results into poor employee productivity and hence poor performance by the company, high employee absenteeism, demonstrations by famers on over delayed payments, closure of some Nzoia outreach offices', incompetence of some information technology employees, field staff carrying out illegal fuel selling and spare parts of the machines, customer complaints reluctantly attended to by employees and the employees generally lack organizational citizenship employee behavior. It is based on this background that this study will investigate the effect of reward programme on employ work motivation at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. Specifically, the study will aim at finding out why the employee work motivation is low despite the existence of reward programme.

2. Statement of the problem

Reward programme is one of the strategies used in organizations to improve employee work morale and subsequent performance. Researchers, practitioners and scholars have established that there is a link between reward programme and employee work motivation. The management of Nzoia Sugar Company limited has established reward programme in their organization; these include promotion, training and development and work flexibility in pursuit of increasing employee work motivation so as to ensure prompt and quality service. However, employee work motivation is still low despite of existence of reward programme, (Nzoia report, 2012). This study therefore, aims at investigating and analyzing how well the current reward programme influence employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company limited in Bungoma County. Specifically, the study will aim at finding out why the employee job performance is low despite the existence of reward programme.

3. Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of current reward programme on employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company limited in Bungoma County. The study investigated and analyzed how well the current reward programme help

generate employees job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company limited in Bungoma County.

4. Objective of the study

1. To establish the influence of employee job promotion on employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County.
2. To establish how training influence employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County.
3. To examine how the influence of flexible work programs on employee job performance at Nzoia sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County.
4. To assess the extent to which incentives and bonus influence employees job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County.

4.1 Research Questions

1. What is the influence of employee job promotion programs on employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County?
2. To which extent does training influence the employee jobperformance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County?
3. What is the effect of flexible work reward programs on employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County?
4. To what extend does incentive influence employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County?

5. Literature Review

5.1 Concept of employee reward and job performance

Vroom suggested that individuals will choose behavior they will result in achievement of specific outcomes they value. In deciding how much effort to put into work behavior, individuals are likely to consider these things; valance, instrumentality and expectancy. All these factors are referred to as "VIE" and they are considered to influence motivation in a combined manner.

The relevance of this to the study is the Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County has put up rewards that are supposed to be attractive so as to achieve a desired employee work motivation and performance. In this study, the hygiene theory is suitable. It states that intrinsic factors are related to job satisfaction while extrinsic factors are related to dissatisfaction. Herzberg's motivators are factors that motivate

employees to the highest level of performance. These motivators are an integral part of the work itself and include factors such as the nature of work, person's sense of achievement, personal development, recognition and feedback (Schultz, 1982). The relevance of Herzberg's theory to this study is that, the discussion of reward is that a dissatisfied employee cannot be motivated. It is thus important that Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County first give attention to hygiene factors before introducing motivators into workplace.

5.2 Promotion and employee job performance

Promotion exerts a long lasting thought on employees and keeps on demonstrating the employee's opinion that they appreciated (Silbert, 2005, cited in Madiha et al; 2009). Promotion plays a significant role in job satisfaction as they accomplish the necessities as well as facilitate to achieve the higher level of motivation.

According to (Bokemeier and Lucy, 1986, Madiha et al, 2009), argue that promotion signify that employees are achieving by devoting their precious time, efforts and skills in their job performance. A similar view of study is shown by (Bamberger and Meshoulum, 2000), he argues that the promotion programme influence the employee performance and their aspiration to stay. Extremely promotion programme endorse to employee commitment and consequently attract and retain superior workforce (Zhao and Kay, 2008). Some studies dispute promotion programme that may not improve employee motivation if not well addressed. According to (Woodruffe, 1999), argue that a major difference among workers exists in acknowledging the worth of promotion for employee performance and contribution.

Eisenberger and Armeli (1997) argue that promotion can be used to convey important information to employees and it is this information component that is linked to both performance and ultimately creativity. Thus, promotion should be seen as something given in recognition of individuals competence, attempts to engage in creative activity and their creative accomplishments.

Employees become more involved in successful outcomes where they know they will be promoted. This will show employees that they are appreciated and recognized. The promotions boost the performance, commitment and motivate the employees to continue with high level of productivity and creativity.

An organization for global manufacturer of broad-name products for consumers needed to improve levels of employee motivation, first in order to improve performance. Managers focused on promotion as the key to raising employee performance and commitment. Every employee could nominate anyone they consider worthy of promotion. Successful employees got promotion and they really felt

appreciated. In the experience of a “promotion” employee, to be promoted formerly gave extra performance and made me wonder what I could do to keep the momentum going” (Gyurcik & Brawley, 2000)

5.3 Training and employee job performance

Individuals require career development opportunities to develop and competencies according to (Prince, 2005, Nadiha et al, 2009), Huselid (1995), argue that Knowledge, skills and ability of prospective employees are enhanced by career development opportunities and training and also improves the quality or efficiency of employees in terms of reduced wastages and increases productivity.

Vroom, (1964), argues that the opinion about prospects development opportunities motivate the employees for up to expectation performance. For recent researchers; it is argued that employees have fewer propensities to leave only if they are learning and developing. Conversely, they instigate to externally seek for better alternative job opportunities (Rodriguez, 2008)

According to Hackman and Oldeman, (1975) argue that career opportunities influence employees performance and attitudes towards work and this in turn creates employees to adhere to organization policy and quality work output. Basudur, Green and Green (1982), argue that training cultivates positive improvement to attitudes associated with divergent thinking of employees. In addition, it encourages creative problem-solving of conflicts among employees which creates conducive climate for working.

According to Kinick (2005), he argues that through training, employees are involved in handling of grievances or complaints in efficient ways. Kanter (1977) determined that a strong controlled developmental opportunity causes employees to separate themselves from their bosses and strongly opposed organizational demands. The management should continuously provide training and development opportunities to employees to develop new skills and ideas to improve or adapt to their performance and keep up with changing technology (Simonsee, 1997).

Scottarade Inc; a firm that deals with financial services delivered superior services care of the employees even in turbulent environment that had gripped the entire financial services industry. The firm had given good performance and industry observers felt that its performance management and reward programme e.g training and development was responsible for this (Purkayastha & Chaudhari, 2011).

A survey of IT professionals working in estate agencies and University of Louisiana USA, conducted in 2002 showed that employees were mostly satisfied with intrinsic factors such as the technical aspects of the work and working with new

technologies. The intellectual challenge and creativity require to solve complex technical problems, the constant learning and master skills related to new technologies and a sense of contribution and pride in their accomplishment (Pawlowski, 2005).

5.4 Employee Work Flexibility and Job Performance

It's widely thought that performance climate give employees the opportunity to progress and develop which is critical factor to employee job performance (Benson, 2006, Jamrog, 2004).

According to Kattsen (1996) in an action research carried out with the objective to develop and implement new performance time arrangement in a sausage plant. The plant had experienced flexible employee sickness and absenteeism. The management decided to encourage flexible employee time arrangement schedule. The employee performance flexibility increase job productivity. Involving employee in setting up time schedule builds employee performance. Hence, improve employee's productivity.

Khan et al (2011) argued that when employees are marking time schedule of duties, this in turn influence employee clarity of expectations. The time schedule act as a source of professional challenge boosting the importance of being undertaken and hence improving employee job performance. Increase employee commitment and satisfaction.

According Chndrasekar (2011), argue that performance place environment plays a vital role in motivating employee to perform their assigned work. The working need to be flexible to accommodate the employee needs. For example employees should be capable of controlling, implying development in work assignment, procedures and programs.

Falkum (2003), in his study, argues that employee's participation in marking employee time schedule of performance ensures that employees are adequately motivated to avoid laxity, absenteeism at the work place. He further argues that participation has in employee resistance and employee indifference as a neutral in-between categories. The performance of employee depends on what employee take in work flexibility influences individual's motivation and attitude towards motivation (Hackman and Oldman, 1975).

Oldam and Cummings (1996), argue that the way jobs are structured contributes employee intrinsic motivation and creative output at work. Jobs that are complete and demanding allow employees to be flexible and encourage them to try new ways of doing things, to take risks and potentially to perform creatively. In support of his Shelley et al (2000), found that when performance environment complement the

creative requirements of job individuals had higher job satisfaction and hence performance.

European journal of business and management, Vol. 3 No. 12, 2011, argues that active environment that allow flexibility fosters high levels of both employee and job control psychological demands, that enhance high job performance and encouragement of employee to learn more sophisticated, easy and behaving different in different situation which ultimately leads to higher level of job performance with efficient and increased productivity.

Usmanand Ismail (2010), studied environment that can impact stress on employee job performance, a case study of banking sector of Parkistan. He argue that employee job performance has negative relation between them

There is a positive association among performance outcome, public employees' motivation and performance related pay designs (Paarsch and Shearer 2000) whereas Wright (2007) implied positive relationship between the availability of extrinsic reward e. g work flexibility and employee job performance. In constant, there is in significant relationship between extrinsic reward and employee job performance (Tippet & Kluvers, 2009). This is also supported by Deci, Koestner and Ryan (1999), the extrinsic Kreward had a significant negative influence on intrinsic rewards.

A survey also shows that the employees were satisfied with extrinsic factors, such as working environment, and the professional performance climate, and flexible or normal work hours (Pawloski, Suzanne Datta, and Pratine Houston, 2005). Another study performance by Baer, Oldham and Cummings, (2003) showed that extrinsic rewards were positive for employees occupying simple jobs and negative for employees having jobs that were difficult and challenging. Intrinsic benefits that arise from the job content itself and have consequences for the psychological development of the employee (Williamson, Barnett & Bartol, 2009). It would appear that the greatest amount of performance is presented when people perform tasks that are both intrinsically and extrinsically rewarding (Lawler, 2003).

5.5 Theoretical Review

Rewards have been shown to motivate employees, when certain conditions exist (Blinder, 1990). Individuals are best motivated when they believe that behavior will lead to certain outcomes that are attractive. Job performance therefore best explains element of reward the influence it has on performance. This study will be based on the following motivational theory.

5.6 Conceptual framework

As this study, it examines the relationship between reward programs and employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. Employee job performance taken as the dependent variable while reward programs is taken as independent variable. The frame work of the proposed conceptual mode is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: The conceptual frame work showing the relationship between reward system and employee job performance

Source: Researchers conceptualization

Independent variables are factors that the researcher manipulates in order to determine their influence on employees job performance. These include training, promotion, work flexibility and incentive.

Dependent variable is a variable that varies as a function of independent variables (Mugenda and Mugenda 1999). In this case, job performance depends on independent variable shown in figure 1.

Moderating variables is a factor that alters the impact of an independent on a dependent variable. It is like a catalyst, in this study the variables are; company act, government policies and workers union.

5.7 Summary of the literature review

A lot of work has been done in evaluating relation between reward and employee job performance. In orders to maximize the performance of the employees, organizations must make such policies and procedures and formulate such rewards and those policies and procedures which increase employee satisfaction and job performance (Hafiza et al, 2011)

Sometimes management pays more attention to extrinsic rewards but intrinsic rewards are equally important in employee job performance. Intangible rewards like appreciation and recognition plays a vital role in motivating employees and increasing his performance. From the study by Badrinarayan and Tilekar (2011) it was found that security, career development has a very positive impact on job performance; there was a positive relation between rewards, recognition and job performance. Robert, (2005). However, Andrew (2004) concludes that commitment of employee is based on rewards.

5.8 Knowledge gap

Research has concentrated on the employees' satisfaction with the employer and the company not the reward programs. This study therefore intends to fill the gap by carrying out this current research to establish the influence of current reward programs on employee performance Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. In the study on influence of reward programs on employee performance, a case in Kenya power and lighting company limited, Nakuru Kenya (Njanja, Maina, Ribet and Njagi, 2012), the study did not focus on all reward programs but only focused on cash bonuses. They argued that motivation is personal and what motivates one employee could be different from what motivates the rest. Therefore, they recommended further research studies to be carried out on other reward programs. This study therefore will seek to fill this knowledge based gap on influence of other reward programs on employee job performamnce at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County.

The study on the impact of reward programs on employee performance in Motonet-Espoo, of Finland (Mikander, 2010). The researcher observed that there was little research literature on employee attitude towards reward programs and employee performance; she further recommended that further research be conducted on effect of reward programs on employee performance on a more particular level. This study therefore intends to fill this knowledge gap by carrying out this current research on influence of current reward programs on employee performance.

6. Research Methodology

6.1 Research design

The study employed descriptive research design because; the design involves observing and describing the behavior of the subject without influencing it in any way. It was also used because the subject is only measured once. According to Cooper and Schindler (2003), a descriptive research design is concerned with finding out what, where and how of a phenomena's. The design investigated the effects of current reward programs on employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited, Bungoma County.

The descriptive design allowed the result to be presented through simple statistics, table, mean scores, percentages and frequency distributions, (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). The study described the influence of reward program on employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2003). Survey strategy is a deductive approach popular in business research. The main advantage this research is the ability to collect large amount of data from sizeable population in a highly economical way.

The independent variable in the study is the reward programs while dependent variable being employee job performance. The independent variable is one that the researcher manipulates. It is what the researcher changes to cause a certain influence, while dependent variable is employee job performance one that the researcher observes or measures.

6.2 Target Population

The area of the study was at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited employees in Bungoma County. The Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County was chosen by the researcher because the area was nearer and the travelling costs and other expenses was minimized. Secondly, the area of study was picked by the researcher because the company is suitable for what the research intends to study. To researcher, the study

area provides for the collection of relevant information with minimal expenditure of effort, time and money.

The study population included 252 employees of Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. They were sampled from key department in Human Resource Management, finance, planning and Technical departments. The population targeted both men and women employed by Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. The study also targeted permanent and casual employees. Each department produced 25% of target of top management staff, 30% of middle management staff and 30% of lower cadre of staff.

6.3 Sampling procedure and sample size

6.3.1 Sampling procedure

The study used stratified random sampling to select employees at Nzoia Sugar Company limited in Bungoma County. The technique provides equal opportunity of selection for each element in a population. Randomization is effective in creating equivalent representative groups that are essentially the same on all relevant variables thought of by the researcher (Amina, 2005).

6.3.2 Study sample size determination

The 30% study sample size was obtained from population of 252. A study sample of 30% was selected from each strata in population that each stratum bears to study population. The 30% was selected because it gives adequate information that could be easily interpreted. It also fulfills minimum study sample suggested by Putton (2002) who recommended 30% of the target population as an adequate study sample size in a descriptive study survey research.

This generated a sample size of 76 respondents which the study sought information from. The sample size was therefore 76 respondents. Each level of employees formed the strata and from each stratum the respondents was chosen randomly. Each department produced 30% of the sample size of top management staff, 30% of middle management staff and 30% of lower cadre of staff of the sample size.

6.4 Research instruments

Both the close ended questions and open ended questions were used. The close ended questions included all possible answers/pre-written response categories and respondents were asked to choose among them. For example, scale questions. The advantage of close ended questions allow the ease entering of data into a computer for

analysis, greater number can be distributed, easy to fill, save time and keep respondents focused on the subject.

The open-ended questions allowed respondents have no standard answers and therefore data analysis was more complex. In study, the close-ended questions with boxes to tick or scales to rank were constructed first and then finish with the section open-ended questionnaire methods are chosen because they are flexible and time saving.

The questionnaire also included both structured and unstructured questions. The structured questions was also used as an effort to conserve time, money and to facilitate an easier analysis as they were in immediate usable form, while unstructured questions was used to encourage the respondent to give deep response without feeling hold back in revealing of any information. The questionnaire took care of the respondents' opinions and attitude on the effect of current rewards programme on employee performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. The unstructured questions required probing which called for self-administered questionnaire presented by the interviewer. The method ensured high respondents rate and gave benefits of degree of personal contact.

The quantitative research method adopted structured questions. In this questionnaire, the items were accompanied by a list of all possible attentions from which respondents selected the answer that best described the situation. The questions were easy to answer, economical on time and money. The structural questions were mailed to the correspondents. Self-administered envelopes and stamps accompanied the questionnaire. This saved time and costs. The questionnaire consisted of section A which contained structured items on the personal details of the respondent. Section B comprised of structured items on employee satisfaction with Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County reward programme. Section C consisted of structured questions on measures of overall employee job performance. Section D consisted of unstructured items on effective ways on improving reward programmes in Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. Adequate questionnaire is critical to success of research. Inappropriate questions, incorrect sealing, incorrect ordering of questions, can make the research valueless as it may not accurately reflect the views of participants.

6.5 Pilot Study

The pilot study was carried out on employees of Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. The pilot study aimed at determining reliability of the questionnaire including the wording, structure and sequence of the questions (Ngechu, 2004). The pilot study involved 5% respondent in the population and they were not part of the

main sample size. This means 8 respondents were chosen using stratified random sampling technique. The purpose of the study was to rephrase the questionnaire so that respondent in the main study could not have any problems in answering questions.

6.6 Instrument validity

Validity is the extent to which the instrument collects accurate data that it is meant to collect. The study used content validity. Further, validity was enhanced by applying the correct procedure to find responses to the set items that rely on the set objectives of the study. The content validity was based on the use of appropriate vocabulary sentence structure, whether the questions were suitable for the intended respondents.

6.7 Instrument reliability

To ensure reliability, the questionnaire was pre-tested on eight (8) respondents at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. Reliability is the degree to which a research instruments yields consistent results after repeated trials. The objective of pre-testing is to allow modification of various questions in order to rephrase, clarify and clear up any shortcoming in the questionnaire. In the study Cronbach Alpha reliability co-efficient was computed to indicate how reliable the instruments were.

A co-efficient of 0.7 or more will imply that there is a high degree of data reliability. Sometimes a researcher may get away with using less reliable data if the sample size is very big or the variables under study differ greatly among the subject. But where the sample size and variations are small a highly reliable data set is required to reveal the magnitude of this variation.

In order to test reliability of the instrument to be used in the study will be completed and the reliability co-efficient is calculated. This was established to the extent in which the questionnaire was elicited the same response every time it was administered. A correlation co-efficient of 0.5 if arrived at, then it will be considered reliable for the study.

If all items are perfectly reliable and measure the same thing, then co-efficient alpha is equal to 1. The Cronbach Alpha is the most form of internal consistency reliability co-efficient.

By correction, a lenient cut off of 0.6 is common to explanatory research; alpha should be at least 0.7 or higher to retain an item as an adequate scale and many researchers require a cut off of 0.7 for good scale. Regarding the above explanation in this research Cranach's alpha was used in order to the consistency of the items at the items at the pilot study, after calculating this the researcher made the relevant changes

in order to make the questionnaire reliable and bring the Cronbach Alpha to minimum of 0.7.

6.8 Data collection procedure

The study used questionnaires to collect primary data. The quantitative data were collected by self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed basing on the study objectives so as to provide correct information for the study. The researcher obtained authority letter from Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County. The questionnaire was issued by the researcher to the respondent comprising of the top management staff, middle management staff and lower cadre staff. The respondents were given two weeks to complete the questionnaire. The researcher also used interviews schedules to get information.

6.9 Data analysis techniques

Data from proposed research were coded, processed and analyzed using computer based statistical package for social sciences (SPSS)

Chi-square was used to establish relationship between two variables both of which were categorical in nature. Specifically, it sought to establish the degree to which reward programme influence employee job performance. The contingency table was used to analyze and record between two or more variables which are categorical.

Descriptive statistics enabled the research to describe the aggregation of new data in numeral terms (Neuman, 2000). The study used five point likert scale ranging from 1=strong disagreed to 5=strongly agree for items analysis purpose Likert scale is easy to use in respondents centered and stimulus centered studies (Patton 2002).

6.10 Ethical considerations

The study adhered to ethical issues that are the baseline of any researcher adhered to principle of confidentiality. The study reflected respect for the right of self-determination. The description of aggregate or collections guaranteed anonymity of individual respondents. The researcher ensured that there was no harm to the respondents emotionally or psychologically.

Table 1: Operationalization of variables

Objectives	Variables	Indicator	Measurement scale	Type of analysis
To establish the influence of promotions on employee job morale	Independent variable Promotion	Promotions on merit	Ordinal nominal	descriptive

Injendi Wycliffe, Joash Migosi
 INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEES REWARD PROGRAMME ON JOB PERFORMANCE IN
 NZOIA SUGAR COMPANY LIMITED BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA

To establish the influence of training on employees job performance	Training	Workshops and in-service courses, seminars, allow professional growth	Ordinal nominal	Descriptive inferential
To determine the influence of work flexibility on employees work morale	Work flexibility	Working for normal hours and payment of extra hours	Ordinal nominal	Descriptive inferential
To establish the influence of incentives on employees work morale	Incentives	Presence of bonus and holiday allowance, medical schemes and burial benevolent fund	Ordinal nominal	Descriptive
	Dependent variable Job performance	Increased quality, quantity and productivity Lower absenteeism, commitment, job satisfaction		Descriptive

7. Data Analysis, Presentation, Interpretation and Discussion

7.1 Return Rate

Table 2: Response rate

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Responded	56	93.3
Not Responded	4	6.7
Total	60	100.00

The study sought to find out the response rate of the respondents. Findings are presented in table 4.1.

The study targeted 60 respondents in collecting data. Results in table 4.1 shows that 56 out of 60 target respondents filled the questionnaires and returned the question contributing to 93.3% response rate. The response rate was good, representative and conformed to the Mugenda and Mugenda (1999) stipulation that a response rate of 50% is adequate for analysis and reporting; a response rate of 70% and over is excellent. This response rate is adequate for analysis and reporting.

7.2 Distribution of respondents by demographic details

Table 3: Demographic

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	31	55.4%
Female	25	44.6%
Age		
18-25 years	10	17.9%
26-35years	13	23.2%
36-45 years	14	25.0%
Over 45 years	19	33.9%
Level of education		
Certificate	14	25.0
Diploma	11	19.6
Degree	23	41.1
Post graduate	8	14.3
How many years have you been working in your current work task		
Less than 1 year	1	1.8
1-9 years	34	60.7
Over 10 years	21	37.5

It is evident from demographic data that the respondents are able to provide adequate and clear information to guide discussions.

The study sought to find out the demographic details of the respondents, 31(55.4%) were male while 25(44.6%) were female. On their age most 19(33.9%) were over 45 years, 14(25.0%) were between the age 36-45 years, 13(23.2%) were between 26-35 years and 10(17.9%) were between 18-25 years. Most respondents 23(41.1%) on their level of education indicated they have attained a degree, 14(25.0%) indicated they have a certificate, 11(19.6%) indicated a diploma and 8(14.3%) indicated they have a post graduate. Most 34(60.7%) indicated they have worked in their current work task for between 1-9 years, 21(37.5%) indicated they have worked for over 10 years and only 1(1.8%) said less than one year.

7.3 Distribution of respondents by number of years of service

Table 4: No. of Years Working in Nzoia Sugar Company

Years	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 5 years	13	23.2
Between 6- 10 years	6	10.7
Between 11 - 15 years	12	21.4
Between 16-20 years	7	12.5

Above 20 years	18	32.2
----------------	----	------

Source: Primary Data (2016)

The respondents were asked for how many years have they worked in Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County, 18(32.2%) stated over 20 years, 13(23.2%) stated less than 5 years, 12(21.4%) stated between 1 1-5 years, 7(12.5%) stated between 16-20 years and 6(10.7%) stated between 6- 10 years.

Table 5: Place of work for respondents

Department	Frequency	Percent
Sales and marketing	9	16.1
Human Resource	15	26.8
Finance	10	17.9
Public relations	9	16.1
Agriculture and I.T.	12	21.4
No response	1	1.8
Total	56	100.0

Since the study sought to find out the departments that the respondents worked in, most 15(26.8%) worked in the Human Resource department, 12(21.4%) stated agriculture and IT, 10(17.9%) stated finance, 9(16.1%) stated sales and marketing and another 9(16.1%) stated public relations.

This goes on to show that most of the workers are assigned duties in the human resource department, followed by those in the agriculture and IT.

7.4 Distribution of respondents according to job title

Table 6: Distribution of the Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percent
Manager	4	7.1
Head of Department	7	12.5
Section Head	12	21.4
Supervisor	14	25.0
Any other	19	33.9
Total	56	100.0

The respondents were asked what their designation are in the company and 19(33.9%) stated Other supporting staff, 14(25.0%) stated they are supervisors, 12(21.4%) stated they are section heads while 7(12.5%) stated they work as head of departments and 4(7.1%) work as managers.

Most of the workers interviewed work as support staff.

7.5 Organizational work flexibility and job performance

Table 7: Organizational work flexibility on rewards programme implementation

Statements	(5) Strongly Agree	(4) Agree	(3) Undecided	(2) Disagree	(1) Strongly Disagree	Means	Rank
The employees subscribe to company's mission statement	26(46.4%)	19(33.9%)	2(3.6%)	7(12.5%)	1(1.8%)	45.4	2
Employees are involved in the making of rules and regulations.	11(19.6%)	21(37.5%)	2(3.6%)	20(35.7%)	2(3.6%)	37.4	8
Management only is involved in making rules and regulation.	13(23.2%)	11(19.6%)	4(7.1%)	17(30.4%)	11(19.6%)	32.2	12
The rules and regulations are applied Discriminatively to the staff or employees	4(7.1%)	15(26.8%)	4(7.1%)	17(30.4%)	16(28.6%)	24.4	5
The staff offers resistance to the rules and regulations applied	2(3.6%)	15(26.8%)	4(7.1%)	26(46.4%)	9(16.1%)	28.4	17
The staff shows high level of compliance to the rules and regulations applied.	15(26.8%)	16(28.6%)	6(10.7%)	17(30.4%)	2(3.6%)	28.6	7
The company has fully endorsed operational manuals and guides on key success areas	22(39.3%)	17(30.4%)	6(10.7%)	9(16.1%)	2(3.6%)	43.2	3
The manual are developed by staff participation	11(19.6%)	20(35.7%)	13(23.2%)	5(8.9%)	4(7.1%)	37.6	8
The company recognizes talent of staff	13(23.2%)	29(51.8%)	13(23.2%)	5(8.9%)	4(7.1%)	46.8	1
The company rewards or compensates competency of the staff.	12(21.4%)	19(33.9%)	1(1.8%)	19(33.9%)	5(8.9%)	36.4	10
The job is well designed and developed	9(16.1%)	23(41.1%)	7(12.5%)	15(26.8%)	4(7.1%)	38.4	7
The company uses monetary rewards to encourage new ideas and models in performance of	9(16.1%)	16(28.6%)	5(8.6%)	21(37.5%)	5(8.9%)	33.6	11

Injendi Wycliffe, Joash Migosi
 INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEES REWARD PROGRAMME ON JOB PERFORMANCE IN
 NZOIA SUGAR COMPANY LIMITED BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA

Duties.							
Promotions in based on competencies and New ideas.	5(8.9%)	17(30.4%)	8(14.3%)	19(33.9%)	6(10.7%)	32.2	13
A recommendation Of the staff is purely based on outstanding performance and New ideas.	5(8.9%)	12(21.4%)	7(12.5%)	28(50.0%)	4(7.1%)	30.8	16
Employees / staff are involved in companies or departmental decision making.	10(17.9%)	25(44.6%)	4(7.1%)	7(12.5%)	9(16.1%)	37	9
The company embraces pooling of opinions as a means of involvement in decision making.	13(23.2%)	23(41.1%)	6(10.7%)	12(21.4%)	2(3.6%)	40.2	5
The company uses direct consultation as a Means involvement decision making.	18(32.1%)	16(28.6%)	4 (7.1%)	14(25.0%)	2(3.6%)	39.2	6
The company use written communication as a means of involvement in decision making.	22(39.3%)	18(32.1%)	2(3.6%)	9(16.1%)	5(8.9%)	42.2	4
Everybody is in charge of reward programme implementation	9(16.1%)	12(21.4%)	5(8.9%)	19(33.9%)	11(19.6%)	31.4	14
Specifically implementation unit is in charge of reward programme implementation	7(12.5%)	14(25.0%)	7(12.5%)	19(33.9%)	5(8.9%)	31	15
External experts are in charge of rewards programme implementation.	7(12.5%)	4(7.1%)	9(16.1%)	25(44.6%)	11(19.6%)	38.8	18
Select management team is in charge of reward programme implementation	13(23.2%)	15(26.8%)	11(19.6%)	6(10.7%)	11(19.6%)	36.2	10

The respondents were asked to rate how strongly they agree or disagree with each of the following statements on aspects of organizational culture on rewards programme

implementation, 26(46.4%) strongly agreed that the employees subscribe to company's mission statement, 21(37.5%) agreed employees are involved in the making of rules and regulations, 17(30.4%) disagreed that management only are involved in making rules and regulation, 17(30.4%) disagreed that the rules and regulations are applied discriminatively to the staff or employees while 26(46.4%) also disagreed that the staff offers resistance to the rules and regulations applied and 17(30.4%) disagreed that the staff shows high level of compliance to the rules and regulations applied.

22(39.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the company has fully endorsed operational manuals and guides on key success areas, 20 (35.7%) agreed that the manual are developed by staff participation, 29(51.8%) agreed that the company recognizes talent of staff, 19(33.9%) agreed that the company rewards or compensates competency of the staff, 35(62.5%) agreed that the company arranges for training time for the staff with 29(51.8%) agreed that the management delegates duties or responsibilities to the juniors staff and 21(37.5%) disagreed that the company uses monetary rewards to encourage new ideas and models in performance of duties. 19(33.9%) disagreed that promotions in based on competencies and new ideas, 28(50.0%) disagreed that a recommendation of the staff is purely based on outstanding performance and new ideas, 25(44.6%) agreed that employees / staff are involved in companies or departmental decision making while 23(41.1%) agreed that the company embraces pooling of opinions as a means of involvement in decision making with 25(44.6%) strongly agreed that the company uses regular staff meetings as a means involvement in decision making and 18(32.1%) strongly agreed that the company uses direct consultation as a means involvement in decision making. 22(39.23) strongly agreed that the company use written communication as a means of involvement indecision making, 19(33.9%) disagreed that everybody is in charge of rewards programme implementation, 19(33.9%) disagreed that they specifically implementation unit is in charge of rewards programme implementation while 25(44.6%) disagreed that external experts are in charge of reward implementation and 15(26.8%) agreed that elect management team is in charge of rewards programme implementation. The company recognizes staff talents was ranked position with 46.8% while the staff offers resistance to rules and regulations was ranked least in position 17 with 28.2%

7.6 Promotion programme and employee job performance

Table 8: Organizational promotion and job promotion

Statements	(5) Strongly Agree	(4) Agree	(3) Undecided	(2) Disagree	(1) Strongly Disagree	Mean	Rank
Authority is fairly decentralized	12(21.4%)	18(32.1%)	5(8.9%)	12(21.4%)	9(16.1%)	36	6
Authority is unfairly shared	6 (10.7%)	19(33.9%)	6(10.7%)	13(23.2%)	12(21.4%)	32.4	7
Authority is centralized	11(19.6%)	13(23.2%)	3(5.4%)	17(30.4%)	12(21.4%)	32.4	8
No legitimate power vested in staff	2 (3.6%)	16(28.6%)	7(12.5%)	16(28.6%)	10(17.9%)	37.4	11
Fewer employees report to me directly	6(10.7%)	11(19.6%)	12(21.4%)	14(25.0%)	10(17.9%)	29.6	10
Many employees reports to me directly	7(12.5%)	12(21.4%)	14(25.0%)	8(14.3%)	12(21.4%)	30.6	9
My span of control compromise my operational effectiveness organizational promotion	4(7.1%)	23(41.1%)	12(21.4%)	13(23.2%)	2(3.6%)	35.6	7
Political inferences in organization influences rewards programme implementation.	35(62.5%)	11(19.6%)	1(1.8%)	5(8.9%)	4(7.1%)	47.2	1
It is difficult to access communication feedback from the top management of the authority.	18 (32.1%)	13(23.2%)	3(5.4%)	18(32.1%)	4(7.1%)	38.2	4

Injendi Wycliffe, Joash Migosi
 INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEES REWARD PROGRAMME ON JOB PERFORMANCE IN
 NZOIA SUGAR COMPANY LIMITED BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA

The difficult in accessing communication feedback affects negatively the attainment of performance goals.	15 (28.6%)	15(28.6%)	5(8.9%)	14(25.0%)	7(12.5%)	39	3
Organizational structured not fit for rewards programme execution	16(28.6%)	15(28.6%)	4(7.1%)	17(30.4%)	4(7.1%)	38	5
The employees strategy towards common goal is very strong.	11(19.6%)	23(41.1%)	7(12.5%)	12(21.4%)	3(5.4%)	39	3
The company reviews Organizational promotion on demand towards ensuring compliance with intended goals.	19(33.9%)	19(33.9%)	5(8.9%)	10(17.9%)	3(5.4%)	41.8	2
The company does not review Organization promotion at all for the purpose of compliance.	7(12.5%)	13(23.2%)	4(7.1%)	17(30.4%)	15(26.8%)	29.6	10

7.7 Training programme and employee job performance

Table 9: Organizational training and developments on rewards programme implementation

Statements	(5) Strongly Agree	(4) Agree	(3) Undecided	(2) Disagree	(1) Strongly Disagree	Mean	Rank
The top management is highly committed towards rewards programme	21(37.5%)	8(14.3%)	8(14.3%)	17(30.4%)	2(3.6%)	39.6	4
The top	8(14.3%)	18(32.1%)	7(12.5%)	20(35.7%)	3(5.4%)	35.2	7

Injendi Wycliffe, Joash Migosi
 INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEES REWARD PROGRAMME ON JOB PERFORMANCE IN
 NZOIA SUGAR COMPANY LIMITED BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA

management command absolute follower ship in executing rewards programme							
The intranets are used by the management as a means of communicating to the staff.	8(14.3%)	23(41.1%)	7(12.5%)	15(26.8%)	2(3.6%)	37	6
The conflict resolution procedures have positive effects on rewards programme implementation.	15(26.8%)	26(46.4%)	8(14.3%)	4(7.1%)	1(1.8%)	42.4	1
The company ensures that employees are fairly represented in decision making relating to their welfare through sensitizing them adequately.	21(37.5%)	11(19.6%)	4(7.1%)	15(26.8%)	2(3.6%)	38.6	5
The company ensures that employees are fairly represented in decision making relating to their welfare through prior notices.	18(32.1%)	21(37.5%)	2(3.6%)	9(16.1%)	5(8.9%)	40.6	2
The management uses prior consultations in the ensuring that employees are well represented	14(25.0%)	17(30.4%)	8(14.3%)	15(26.8%)	1(1.8%)	38.6	5

Injendi Wycliffe, Joash Migosi
 INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEES REWARD PROGRAMME ON JOB PERFORMANCE IN
 NZOIA SUGAR COMPANY LIMITED BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA

in decision making relating to their welfare.							
The management ensures that employees are well represented in decision making relating to their welfare through use of known representative	15(26.8%)	24(42.9%)	3(5.4%)	8(14.3%)	5(8.9%)	40.2	3
The company's management conflict resolution procedures are fair.	13(23.2%)	16(28.6%)	5(8.9%)	12(21.4%)	5(8.9%)	34.6	8
The management has no special arrangement to ensure that employees are fairly represented in decision making relating to their welfare	6(10.7%)	6(10.7%)	4(7.1%)	17(30.4%)	22(39.3%)	24.4	9

The respondents were asked to rate how strongly they agree or disagree with each of the following statement on aspects of organizational training and development on rewards programme implementation, 21(37.5%) strongly agreed that the top management is highly committed towards rewards programme implementation, 20(35.7%) disagreed that the he top management command absolute follower ship in executing rewards programme 29(51.8%) strongly agreed that the company uses circulars as means of communication between staff and management, 39(69.6%) strongly agreed that the management uses notices and memos when communicating to the staff, 34(60.7%) strongly agreed that staff meeting is commonly used by management as a means of communication, 32(57.1%) strongly agreed that management meetings are used as a means of communication to the staff. Most respondents 23(41.1%) agreed that the intranets are used by the management as a means of communicating to the staff, 16(28.6%) agreed that the company's management

conflict resolution procedures are fair, 26(46.4%) agreed that the conflict resolution procedures have positive effects on rewards programme implementation, 21(37.5%) strongly agreed that the company ensures that employees are fairly represented in decision making relating to their welfare through sensitizing them adequately, 21(37.5%) agreed that the company ensures that employees are fairly represented in decision making relating to their welfare through prior notices while 17(30.4%) agreed that the management uses prior consultations in the ensuring that employees are well represented in decision making relating to their welfare, 24(42.9%) agreed that the management ensures that employees are well represented in decision making relating to their welfare through use of known representatives and 22(39.3%) strongly disagreed that management has no special arrangement to ensure that employees are fairly represented in decision making relating to their welfare Management notices and memos. Political interference influences promotion was ranked the highest with 47.2% while the company does not review promotion was ranked least with 29.6%.

7.8 Aspects of incentives allocation of the company and employee job performance

Table 10: Aspects of incentives allocation of the company

Statements	(5) strongly agree	(4) Agree	(3) Undecided	(2) Disagree	(1) Strongly disagree	Mean	Rank
There is limited budgetary allocation to rewards programme implementation	11(19.6%)	21(37.5%)	5(8.9%)	15(26.8%)	3(5.4%)	37.4	4
The company engages external audit as incentives control to ensure that incentives are used as expected.	15(26.8%)	24(42.9%)	2(3.6%)	8(14.3%)	6(10.7%)	41	1
The company applies regular appraisals as incentives control to ensure that incentives are utilized only for purposed	9(16.1%)	19(33.9%)	8(14.3%)	17(30.4%)	1(1.8%)	36	6

Injendi Wycliffe, Joash Migosi
 INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEES REWARD PROGRAMME ON JOB PERFORMANCE IN
 NZOIA SUGAR COMPANY LIMITED BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA

intended.							
Bench marking is used as incentives control to ensure that incentives are utilized well.	8(14.3%)	20(35.7%)	6(10.7%)	16(28.6%)	5(8.9%)	35	7
The company is efficient on the use of the incentives allocated to rewards programme	5(8.9%)	18(32.1%)	3(5.4%)	24(42.9%)	5(8.9%)	31	8
We do have adequate human capacity to implement our rewards programme	11(19.6%)	18(32.1%)	1(1.8%)	22(39.3%)	4(7.1%)	36.6	5
There is inadequate skills and training	15(26.8%)	18(32.1%)	8(14.3%)	9(16.1%)	6(10.7%)	39	2
Some projected sources of funds have changed necessitating changes in the rewards programme	12(21.4%)	30(53.6%)	8(14.3%)	5(8.9%)	1(1.8%)	33.6	5
Lack of finances has hindered implementation of our rewards programme	19(33.9%)	11(19.6%)	4(7.1%)	18(32.1%)	4(7.1%)	38.2	3

The respondents were asked to rate how strongly they agreed or disagreed with each of the following statement on aspects of organizational worker flexibility of implementation of rewards programme, 20(35.7%) disagreed that organization has a quick way to determine failure rate/success rate of rewards programme implementation, 21(37.5%) disagreed that rewards programme implementation feedback mechanisms are adequate, 23(41.1%) agreed that rewards programme implementation process adheres to set time frame with 21(37.5%) who agreed that rewards programme implementation review process is done on demand to ensure

compliance with set goals and 24(42.9%) disagreed that rewards programme implementation has been always achieved. Rewards programme implementation adheres to set time had the highest rank of 36.4% while reward programme implementation is also a achieved had the least rank of 30.4%

7.9 Multiple linear Regressions

R. is considered to be one measure of the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable; in this case, rewards programme implementation. A value of 0.212 indicates a good level of prediction. From our value of independent variables explain 4.5% of the variability of our dependent variable, rewards programme implementation.

Table 12: Model Summary

Model	R	R. Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.212 ^a	.045	-.055	1.153

Predictors: (Constant). Rewards programme implementation has been always achieved, Authority is decentralized, the top management is highly committed towards rewards programme implementation, there is limited budgetary allocation to rewards programme implementation, the employees subscribe to company's mission statement. The F-ration in the ANOVA table below test whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The table shows that the independent variables statistically not significantly predict the dependents variable, $F(5, 48) = .450, p > .0005$ this means that the regression model is not a good fit of the data.

Table 13: AVONA^a

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F.	Sig
Regression	2.990	5	.598	.450	.811 ^b
1 Residual	63.825	48	1.330		
Total	66.815	53			

Dependents variable: Rewards programme implementation feedback mechanisms are adequate.

Predictors: (constant), rewards programme implementation has been always achieved, Authority is fairly decentralized, the top management is highly committed towards rewards programme implementation, there is limited budgetary allocation to rewards programme implementation, and the employees subscribe to company's mission statement

From the "Sig" column in the table below all independents variable coefficients are statistically not significantly different from 0 (Zero). Since the $p > .05$, the study can conclude that the coefficients are statically not significantly to 0 (Zero). Hence the multiple linear regression predict rewards programme implementation from the employees subscribe to company's mission statement (Organizational culture) is fairly decentralized (Organization promotion), the top management is highly committed toward rewards programme implementation (training and developments) and there is limited budgetary allocation to rewards programme implementation (incentives allocation). These variables do not statistically significantly predict rewards programme implementation, $F(5, 48) = .450, p > .0005, R^2 = .450$. All five variables are not statistically significantly to the prediction, $p > .05$.

Model	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig	95.0% confidence interval for B	
	Beta	Std Error	Beta			Lower bound	Upper bound
(constant)	2.287		.857	2.668	.010	.563	4.001
Organization culture	.189	.159	.185	1.184	.242	-.132	.509
Organization promotion	.003	.121	.004	.023	.982	-.240	.246
Training and development	-.055	.126	-.068	-.439	.663	-.308	.198
Incentives allocation	-.052	.138	-.058	-.377	.708	-.330	.226
Rewards programme allocation	.145	.140	.158	1.037	.305	-.136	.426

8. Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

The main objective of this study was to investigate the influence of reward programme on employee job performance at Nzoia Sugar Company Limited in Bungoma County.

The study findings showed that the on aspects of organizational culture on rewards programme implementation, employees subscribed to company's mission statement, employees are involved in the making of rules and regulations also the company has fully endorsed operational manuals and guides on key success areas and that the manual are developed by staff participation. It also found the company recognizes talent of staff, the company rewards or compensates competency of the staff while the company arranges for training time for the staff with the management delegates duties or responsibilities to the juniors staff. Most of the employees / staff are involved in companies or departmental decision making while the company embraces

pooling of opinions as a means of involvement in decision making, it also found that the company uses regular staff meetings as a means involvement in decision making. The study found that the company uses direct consultation as a means involvement in decision making, with the majority of the opinion that the company use written communication as a means of involvement in decision making and that elect management team is in charge of rewards programme implementation.

The study findings showed that on aspects of organizational structure on rewards programme implementation, majority felt that authority is fairly decentralized, that authority is unfairly shared, that their span of control compromises their operational effectiveness organizational structure and that political inferences in organization influences rewards programme implementation. It also found out that it is difficult to access communication feedback from the top management of the authority while there is difficulty in accessing communication feedback affects negatively the attainment of performance goals also that organizational promotion not fit for reward programme execution that the employees energy towards common goal is very strong and that the company reviews organizational promotion on demand towards ensuring compliance with intended goals. The study established that the top management is highly committed towards rewards programme implementation while the company uses circulars as means of communication between staff and management with the management using notices and memos when communicating to the staff, majority of the staff meeting is commonly used by management as a means of communication that management meetings are used as a means of communication to the staff also the intranets are used by the management as a means of communicating to the staff and that the company's management conflict resolution procedures are fair. The study found that the conflict resolution procedures have positive effects on rewards programme implementation, most feel that the company ensures that employees are fairly represented in decision making relating to their welfare through sensitizing them adequately while the company ensures that employees are fairly represented in decision making relating to their welfare through prior notices with the management uses prior consultations in the ensuring that employees are well represented in decision making relating to their welfare and that management ensures that employees are well represented in decision making relating to their welfare through use of known representatives.

The study established on aspects of resources allocation of the company most said there is limited budgetary allocation to rewards programme implementation, company use normal internal audit as resource control to ensure that resources are utilized for purposes intended and that the company engages external audit as

incentives control to ensure that incentives are used as expected. It also found that the company applies regular appraisals as resource control to ensure that incentives are utilized only for purposes intended while bench marking is used as incentives control to ensure that incentives are utilized well also the company offers training and development opportunities to employees so as to sustain efficiency in executing rewards programme and that there is in adequate skills and training. Most employees feel that some projected sources of funds have changed necessitating changes in the rewards programme that employees are highly motivated to facilitate effective rewards programme execution and that lack of finances has hindered implementation of our rewards programme.

The study found that on aspect of organizational worker flexibility of implementation of rewards programme most of the employees feel that rewards programme implementation favorably influence employee job performance.

8.1 Conclusion

From the research findings, organization promotion has a strong influence on successful rewards programme implementation. This indicates that the organizational promotion highly influences successful rewards programme implementation. Regarding organization culture, the study established that there exists a great influence towards successful rewards programme implementation. The study found that organizations should plough a culture that will spearhead the organization towards achieving successful rewards programme implementation.

On whether corporate leadership influences successful rewards, programme implementation as inferred in this study found that corporate leadership is vital for successful rewards programme implementation.

In addition, committed leadership enhances motivation to employees that spearheads successful rewards programme implementation. The study findings indicate that management style of the managers in the process of implementing in the performance system affects the process of rewards programme implementation to a great extent. In addition, managerial commitment speeds up the process of 'rewards programme implementation likewise management style affects the speed and the effectiveness of the rewards programme implementation.

8.2 Recommendations for policy and practice

The study makes specific recommendations guided by the objectives of the study and which are workable and tentative in nature if implemented by the stakeholders as identified in the study.

The study recommends Nzoia Sugar Company creates a higher level of involvement of staff members in any further rewards programme development and review to avoid hands off approach and lack of ownership on their part. It is also critical that a review is done to distinguish between rewards programme implementation and other performance and Quality management tools such as performance contracting and ISO certification processes. There is also need to institutionalize policies so that their guiding philosophies are shared across the staff and to avoid them being viewed as managerial propensity to lord over staff. The staff should be motivated to learn new knowledge on the role place of rewards programme management in steering organizations to rewards advantage in times of volatile market conditions. There is motivation in knowing you can control dynamic managerial challenges as with time one may become the Manager of the situations or even the organization. Staff members must also be objectively critical to managerial leadership styles as this has far reaching implications which could ruin individual reputations where ones current station under performs persistently. The failure tag would be part of one history and not good for professional development or progress.

Poor understanding of rewards among employees and ineffective communication of the rewards programme to the workforce are the most vital barriers to effective rewards programme implementation.

The study recommends that employees in the sugar sectors be sensitized on need to be committed to the successful rewards programme implementation process. They should be also trained so as to be able to understand and carry out the implementation process well and effectively.

The management style was found to have profound effects on the speed and the extent of implementation of rewards programme. This study recommends that the various levels of management be fully engaged in the implementation efforts of rewards programme so as to make the systems more effective.

References

1. Ali, R. & Ahmed, M. (2008). The impact of reward programme and recognition programs on employees' motivation and satisfaction.
2. Badrinarayan S.R & Tilekar, P. (2011). Critical analysis of motivators and hygiene factors with special reference to employees of private and public sector. Banks in India, international journal of research in IT & management, I (I) pp 39-50.
3. Ballentine, A. (2003). Non-motery rewards in the work place.

4. Bohlander, E. Snell, S. & Sherman, A. (2001). *Managing human resources* (12th edition). London South Western College.
5. Cameron J. & Pierce W. D. (2006). *Rewards and intrinsic motivation; resolving the controversy*. United States; Bergin & Garvey.
6. Copper, D. and Schindler, P. (2003). *Business research methods*, (6th Edition). Macraw Hill Irwin.
7. Finkle L. (2011). *Motivating employee performance through year end-bonuses*.
8. Golosorkhi, D., Rouleau, L. Seidl, D. & Vaara, E. (2010). *Cambridge handbook of Strategy as practice* New York, Cambridge University press.
9. Government of Kenya, (20 12). *Development of Education, National Report of Kenya* Nairobi University of Education 63-1 12.
10. Hafiza, N. S. Shah, S. Jamsheed, H. & Zaman K. (2011). *Relationship between reward and employees motivation in the non-profit organization of Pakistan*. *Business intelligence journal* 4(2) pages 327-334.
11. Hrebiniak, I, (2008). *Making strategy work: Overcoming the obstacle to effective execution*, *Ivey Business Journal*, 72 (2), 1-6.
12. Jarzabkowaski, P, & Spee, P. (2009). *Strategy as practice: A reviews and future directions for the field* *International Journal of Management Reviews* 11 (I), 69-95.
13. John M. Bryson, (2010). *Creating and implementing your strategic plans: a workbook for Public and non-Profit organizations* 2nd edition.
14. Jones, R; (20 12). *Strategic planning; keep it from failing*
15. Kankanhalli, A. Tan, B. C. Y. & wei K. K. (2005). *Contributing knowledge to electronic knowledge repositories. An empirical investigation* *MIS quarterly*, 29 (1)pp 113-143.
16. Kauvenhoven, R., & Buss, C. W. (201 1). *A normative view of the role of middle managements in the implementation of strategy change* *journal of management & marketing research*, 81-14.
17. Kirk, Jerome & Miller, mark L. 1986. *Reliability and validity in quantitative research*, 1st Edition USA sage publication Inc, page 87.
18. Kotelnikov, V. (2010). *Reward programme and job performance effective reward Programme increasing: performance & creating happier employees*. Retrieved from <http://www.1000ventures.com/businessguide/cross-cuttings/motivating-rewardprogramme.html>.
19. Kothari. C. I. C. (2007). *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques*. New Delhi; New age International Publishers.

20. Kotter, B. and Best, H. (2006). Management by policy. How companies focus their total quality efforts to achieve competitive advance, Milwaukee: ASQC quality press.
21. Lawler E. E. (2003). Treat people right. San Francisco; Jossey-Bass Inc.
22. Magenda, O. M. and Magenda, A.G (2003). Research methods; Qualitative and quantitative approaches. Nairobi; Acts press.
23. Mintzberg, H, (2003). Structure in fives designing effective organizations, prentice Hall, Englewood. Cliffs, NJ. 49.
24. Morris, J. (2007). The art of employee motivation. Retrieved from <http://sourcesmasterblogpot.com/2007/06/artofemployeemotivation.html>
25. Munyasi, N. B. (2009) Crisis management: A challenge in Institutions of higher learning in Kenya: A conference paper is presented at the 1st Kim conference on management: A journal of the Kim School of management: TSSN 2070-4730
26. Ngware, N, W, Wamukuru, D.K and Odebero S.O. (2006). Total Quality management in secondary schools in Kenya; Extent of practice quality Assurance in Education, Vol. 14 No.40pp 339 362.
27. Noble, C.H. (1999). Building the strategy implementation network Business Horizons, 42 (6),19.
28. Normand, B. (2010). How to design a good incentive plan. Retrieved from <http://www.businessperform.com/articles/inentiveplandesign.html>.
29. Panday M. (2005). Balanced scored card: myth and Reality. Vikalpa: The Journal for occasion makers. 30 (I), 51-46.
30. Pawlowski, Suzanne, D. J. Datta, Patrin & Houston, A.L. (2005). The (gradually) changing face of state I.T Jobs. Communications of the A.C.M, 48 (5).
31. Peil M. (1995). Research methods. Handbook for Africa 2nd edition. Nairobi; East Africa Educational publishers.
32. Pettigrew, A. M. (2005). The character and significant of strategy process Researcher strategy management journal 1,3,5,6,
33. Pitts, Collins, (1995), motivating your organization, 1st edition. McGraw-Hill International, page187,
34. Purkayastha, D. & Chaudhari; A. (2011), Performance management and rewards programme.
35. IBS centre for management research. Retrieved from <http://www.ecch.com/educators/productsview?Id=100368>.
36. Rose, W. R. & Cray, D. (201 3). The role of context in the transformation of planned strategy into implemented strategy. Internal Journal of Business of Business management & Economic research 4 (3), 721-737.

37. Roulean, L. & Balogun, J. (2011). Middle managers, strategic sense making, and discursive competence, *Journal of management studies* 48 (5) (953-98)
38. Salih, A; & Doll, Y. (2013). A middle management perspective on strategy implementation *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8 (22), 32-39.
39. Sarvadi, P (2010). The best ways to reward employees. *Entrepreneur magazine*. Retrieved from <http://www.entrepreneur.com/humanresources/article75340.html>
40. Tippet, J. & Kluvers, R. (2009). Employee rewards and motivation in non-profit organization; the case study from Australia *International Journal of Business and Management* 4(3) pages 7-14.
41. Torrington Derek, Hall, Laura, Taylor, Stephen & Atkinson Carol. 2009, *Fundamentals of human resource management* 1st edition Pearson education limited, page 439.
42. Wambui, V. R. (2010). Factors influencing successful implementation of strategic plans of public sectors Sacco Society within Nairobi Region MBA project, Kenyatta University.
43. Yokoyama, M. (2007), *When to use employees incentives*
44. Yritysesitelly, (2009), Motonet, Brouman Group Oy. Available from <http://www.motonet.fi/web/guest/yrtyys.2010>

Injendi Wycliffe, Joash Migosi
INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEES REWARD PROGRAMME ON JOB PERFORMANCE IN
NZOIA SUGAR COMPANY LIMITED BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Social Sciences Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).